

Novel Enzymatic De-esterification Studies on Substituted Polyacetoxybenzamides[†]VIRINDER S. PARMAR^{a*}, AJAY KUMAR^a, ASHOK K. PRASAD^a, RAJESH KUMAR^a, KIRPAL S. BISHT^a, POONAM^a, SUBHASH C. JAIN^a and CARL E. OLSEN^b^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007^bChemistry Department, Royal Veterinary and Agricultural University, DK-1871 Frederiksberg C, Copenhagen, Denmark

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The regioselective capabilities of porcine pancreatic lipase in tetrahydrofuran and *Candida rugosa* lipase in diisopropyl ether have been investigated for selective deacetylation of peracetates of primary, secondary and tertiary amides of 2-hydroxy-, 2,4-dihydroxy-, 2,5-dihydroxy-, 3,5-dihydroxy- and 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acids. The lipases exhibit random selectivity for the deacetylation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-acetoxy functions of di/triacetoxybenzamides leading to the formation of the corresponding partially and/or completely deacetylated benzamides. The amide group of all substrates under investigation remains inert to enzymatic hydrolysis. The results of de-esterification are in good agreement with our earlier proposed mechanism of action of porcine pancreatic lipase on diaryl or aryl alkyl ketones in organic solvents.

The use of enzymes in organic solvents has been well studied in preparative organic chemistry during recent years¹. Among others, lipases have been the most commonly used enzymes to carry out regioselective and/or enantioselective acylation of polyols² and synthesis of chiral intermediates and target molecules³. Though lipases have largely been used to recognise one out of many alcoholic hydroxyl groups in carbohydrates⁴ and aliphatic polyols², such studies have rarely been carried out on phenolic hydroxyl groups. Recently, we have demonstrated that porcine pancreatic lipase (PPL), *Candida rugosa* lipase (CRL) and the *Aspergillus* species lipases⁵ can be used for the regioselective deesterification of peracetates of different classes of polyphenolics, e.g. acetophenones^{6,7}, chalcones⁷, desoxybenzoins^{8,9}, coumarins¹⁰ and flavones¹⁰. It has been observed that the enzyme catalyses the deacetylation of acetoxy groups other than the one at the *ortho* or the *peri* position(s) to the nuclear carbonyl group. This prompted us to postulate that the keto group directly attached to the benzenoid ring forms a transient (dynamic) Schiff's base complex with the ϵ -amino group of the lysine residue in the active site of PPL (in analogy to the human pancreatic lipase), which causes the *ortho*-acetoxy function of the polyacetoxy keto compound to be embedded under the hydrophobic bulk of the active site of the enzyme and at the same time the hydroxy group in the side-chain of serine takes part in deacetylation of other more suitably placed acetoxy function(s) in the molecule¹¹. Very recently, we have substantiated the proposed mechanism of action of PPL by carrying out deacetylation reactions on esters of polyacetoxy aromatic acids¹². Since esters do not form Schiff's bases that easily, therefore PPL failed to recognise the different acetoxy functions in the esters of polyacetoxybenzoic acids and thus products due to random deacetylation were formed.

The amides of aromatic acids form an important class of natural products and frequently show different biological activities^{13,14}. There are many chemical methods for the synthesis of amides of aromatic acids^{15,16}, but most of them are associated with one or the other disadvantages, e.g. requirement of high acidic or basic reaction conditions, high energy consumption, undesirable byproducts and environmentally unfriendly generation of waste salts. Recently, lipases and microorganisms with high concentration of desired enzyme have been used for the synthesis of primary and secondary amides by aminolysis of esters¹⁷ and for the enantioselective hydrolysis of amides¹⁸. However, peracetylated amides of polyhydroxybenzoic acids have not so far been subjected to enzymatic hydrolysis/deacetylation studies. With an aim to study enzymatic deacetylation and to further substantiate our earlier proposed mechanism, we wish to report the results of deacetylation studies on peracetylated primary, secondary and tertiary amides of mono-, di- and trihydroxybenzoic acids catalysed by PPL in tetrahydrofuran (THF) and CRL in diisopropyl ether (DIPE). Several new amides have been synthesised efficiently during the course of this study.

Results and Discussion

2,4-Diacetoxybenzamide (6) and 3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (7) were prepared by aminolysis of the corresponding acetylated benzoyl chlorides (2c and 4c, Scheme 1) with an excess of 30% aq. ammonia¹⁹. Aminolysis of acetylated benzoyl chlorides led to the formation of a mixture of hydroxy- and acetoxybenzamides which on acetylation with an excess of acetic anhydride and catalytic amount of *N,N*-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) afforded the pure peracetylated primary amides 6 and 7. Aminolysis and peracetylation of 2,5-diacetoxybenzoyl chloride (3c) under these conditions

[†]Dedicated with profound love and regards to Professor Sukh Dev on his 75th. birthday.

Scheme 1

afforded *N*-acetyl 2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**21**) exclusively.

Eleven peracetylated secondary amides, i.e. *N*-acetyl-*N*-ethyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (**8**), *N*-acetyl-*N*-ethyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**9**), *N*-ethyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**10**), *N*-4-methylphenyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (**11**), *N*-4-methylphenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**12**), *N*-4-methylphenyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**13**), *N*-4-methylphenyl-3,4,5-trimethoxybenzamide (**14**), *N*-benzyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (**15**), *N*-benzyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**16**), *N*-benzyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**17**) and *N*-benzyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (**18**), and two peracetylated tertiary amides, *N*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-2-acetoxybenzamide (**19**) and *N*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**20**) were prepared by coupling of the corresponding peracetylated aromatic acid chlorides (**1c-5c**, Scheme 1) with primary amines (ethyl-, 4-methylphenyl- and benzylamine) and *N*-methylaniline respectively, in the presence of triethylamine in benzene²⁰. Coupling of primary and secondary amines with acid chlorides **1c-5c** led to the formation of a mixture of hydroxy- and partially acetylated benzamides which on treatment with excess of acetic anhydride and catalytic amount of DMAP afforded pure peracetylated secondary and tertiary amides **10-20**. Treatment of acetylated acid chlorides **2c** and **3c** with ethyl amine followed by acetylation with acetic anhydride and DMAP led to the exclusive formation of *N*-acetylated benzamides **8** and **9**. An attempt towards the preparation of the benzamides **6-21** by aminolysis of hydroxyaromatic acid chlorides or by coupling of the hydroxybenzoic acids **1a-5a** or acetoxybenzoic acids **1b-5b** with ammonia solution or with primary and secondary amines, led to the formation of a polymeric mixture of products which could not be purified and characterised.

The PPL-catalysed deacetylation of 2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (**6**) in THF afforded 2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (**22**) and 2-acetoxy-4-hydroxybenzamide (**23**) in 40 and 30% yields respectively. This is in contrast with the result of deacetylation of 2,4-diacetoxyphenyl methyl ketone under similar conditions where deacetylation of the *ortho*-acetoxy group was not observed⁶. The deacetylation of 3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**7**) catalysed by PPL afforded 3,5-

dihydroxybenzamide (**24**) in 20% yield (Table 1). These results of PPL-catalysed deacetylation of primary benzamides **6** and **7** indicate that the enzyme catalyses the deacetylation of different acetoxy functions, but does not exhibit exclusive selectivity for any one of the *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-acetoxy groups. Thus, during PPL-catalysed deacetylation of 2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (**6**), although the rate of deacetylation of *para*-acetoxy function is faster, the enzyme mediates the de-esterification of *ortho*-acetoxy function as

 TABLE 1—PPL-CATALYSED DEACETYLATION REACTIONS ON AMIDES OF POLYACETOXYBENZOIC ACIDS IN THF AT 42–45° IN THE PRESENCE OF *n*-BUTANOL*

Substrate	Reaction time (day)	Product(s) (% Yield)
2,4-Diacetoxybenzamide (6)	4	2,4-Dihydroxybenzamide (22) (40) and 2-acetoxy-4-hydroxybenzamide (23) (30)
3,5-Diacetoxybenzamide (7)	4	3,5-Dihydroxybenzamide (24) (20)
<i>N</i> -Acetyl- <i>N</i> -ethyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (8)	5	<i>N</i> -Ethyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (25) (15)
<i>N</i> -Acetyl- <i>N</i> -ethyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (9)	5	<i>N</i> -Ethyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (26) (40) and <i>N</i> -ethyl-2,5-dihydroxybenzamide (27) (5)
<i>N</i> -Ethyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (10)	3	<i>N</i> -Ethyl-3-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (28) (20) and <i>N</i> -ethyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (29) (65)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (11)	10	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-4-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (30) (70) and <i>N</i> -4-methylphenyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (31) (5)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (12)	10	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (32) (65) and <i>N</i> -4-methylphenyl-2-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (33) (15)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (13)	4	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (34) (30) and <i>N</i> -4-methylphenyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (35) (35)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (14)	6	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide (36) (30)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (15)	5	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (37) (51)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (16)	5	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (38) (65)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (17)	5	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (39) (95)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (18)	6	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-acetoxy-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (40) and <i>N</i> -benzyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide (41)**

Table-1 (contd.)

<i>N</i> -Methyl- <i>N</i> -phenyl-2-acetoxybenzamide (19)	6	<i>N</i> -Methyl- <i>N</i> -phenyl-2-hydroxybenzamide (42) (49)
<i>N</i> -Methyl- <i>N</i> -phenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (20)	7	<i>N</i> -Methyl- <i>N</i> -phenyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (43) (15)
<i>N</i> -Acetyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (21)	5	<i>N</i> -Acetyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (44) (52)

*No deacetylation reaction was observed on any of the above substrates by carrying out reactions under similar conditions but without addition of PPL.

**Obtained as an inseparable mixture of two in the ratio 3 : 1.

well, and in 3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (7), enzyme deacetylates both the *meta*-acetoxy functions. These results of random deacetylation of *ortho*-, *meta*- and *para*-acetoxy functions of diacetoxybenzamides are expected because the amidic carbonyl can not form Schiff's base¹¹ that easily as the ketonic carbonyl can, thereby leading to random orientation of different acetoxy groups in the active site of PPL, thus resulting in the formation of an *ortho*-hydroxy product together with other possible products. This observation substantiates our earlier proposed hypothesis on the mechanism of action of PPL in THF involving a transient, dynamic Schiff's base complex formation between the ϵ -amino group of the lysine residue in the active site of PPL and the keto group directly attached to the benzenoid ring¹¹. The results of deacetylation catalysed by CRL in DIPE on the two amides 6 and 7 are not different, except for the slower rate of deacetylation of the *ortho*-acetoxy function with respect to that catalysed by PPL (Table 2). Thus, incubation of 2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (6) with CRL afforded 2-acetoxy-4-hydroxybenzamide (23) as a major product (80% yield) and 2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (22) as a minor product (7% yield); CRL like PPL failed to discriminate among the two *meta*-acetoxy functions of 3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (7) affording the dihydroxybenzamide 24 exclusively.

In addition to deacetylation studies on the primary amides 6 and 7, eleven secondary peracetylated amides 8-18 of 2,4-dihydroxy-, 2,5-dihydroxy-, 3,5-dihydroxy- and 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzoic acids were also incubated with PPL and CRL in THF and DIPE respectively, to see the effect of *N*-substituents on the selectivity of the enzyme-catalysed reactions. PPL in THF did not exhibit any selectivity for the deacetylation of *ortho*-, *para*- or *N*-acetoxy functions of *N*-acetyl-*N*-ethyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (8) and resulted in the exclusive formation of *N*-ethyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (25) albeit in low yield. In the case of *N*-acetyl-*N*-ethyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (9), PPL showed preference for the deacetylation of *ortho*-acetoxy function over *meta* and yielded *N*-ethyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (26) as the major product and *N*-ethyl-2,5-dihydroxybenzamide (27) as

- 6; R=R₂=OCOCH₃, R₁=R₃=H
 7; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OCOCH₃
 22; R=R₂=OH, R₁=R₃=H
 23; R=OCOCH₃, R₁=R₃=H, R₂=OH
 24; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OH

- 10; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OCOCH₃
 25; R=R₂=OH, R₁=R₃=H
 26; R=OH, R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃
 27; R=R₃=OH, R₁=R₂=H
 28; R=R₂=H, R₁=OCOCH₃, R₃=OH
 29; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OH

- 8; R=R₁=OCOCH₃, R₂=H
 9; R=R₂=OCOCH₃, R₁=H

- 11; R=R₂=OCOCH₃, R₁=R₃=H
 12; R=R₃=OCOCH₃, R₁=R₂=H
 13; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OCOCH₃
 14; R=H, R₁=R₂=R₃=OCOCH₃
 30; R=OH, R₁=R₃=H, R₂=OCOCH₃
 31; R=R₂=OH, R₁=R₃=H
 32; R=OH, R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃
 33; R=OCOCH₃, R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OH
 34; R=R₂=H, R₁=OCOCH₃, R₃=OH
 35; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OH
 36; R=H, R₁=R₂=R₃=OH

- 15; R=R₂=OCOCH₃, R₁=R₃=H
 16; R=R₃=OCOCH₃, R₁=R₂=H
 17; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OCOCH₃
 18; R=H, R₁=R₂=R₃=OCOCH₃
 37; R=OH, R₁=R₃=H, R₂=OCOCH₃
 38; R=OH, R₁=R₂=H, R₃=OCOCH₃
 39; R=R₂=H, R₁=R₃=OH
 40; R=H, R₁=R₃=OH, R₂=OCOCH₃
 41; R=H, R₁=R₂=R₃=OH
 45; R=R₂=OH, R₁=R₃=H
 46; R=R₃=OH, R₁=R₂=H

the minor product (Table 1). PPL discriminates between the two equivalent *meta*-acetoxy groups in the secondary amide, *N*-ethyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (10) leading to the formation of *N*-ethyl-3-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (28) alongwith *N*-ethyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (29) in 20 and 65% yields respectively. The selectivity of CRL in DIPE is comparable to that of PPL in THF for the deacetylation of acetoxy functions of 8 and 9 leading to the formation of *N*-ethyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (25) and *N*-ethyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (26) in 12 and 50% yields respectively (Table 2). CRL failed to discriminate among the two *meta*-acetoxy functions of *N*-ethyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (10) and afforded the dihydroxybenzamide 29 in 95% yield.

TABLE 2—CRL-CATALYSED DEACETYLATION REACTIONS ON AMIDES OF POLYACETOXYBENZOIC ACIDS IN DIPE AT 42–45° IN THE PRESENCE OF *n*-BUTANOL*

Substrate	Reaction time (day)	Product(s) (% Yield)
2,4-Diacetoxybenzamide (6)	6	2,4-Dihydroxybenzamide (22) (7) and 2-acetoxy-4-hydroxybenzamide (23) (80)

Table-2 (contd.)

3,5-Diacetoxybenzamide (7)	4	3,5-Dihydroxybenzamide (24) (15)
<i>N</i> -Ethyl- <i>N</i> -acetyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (8)	5	<i>N</i> -Ethyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (25) (12)
<i>N</i> -Ethyl- <i>N</i> -acetyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (9)	5	<i>N</i> -Ethyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (26) (50)
<i>N</i> -Ethyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (10)	4	<i>N</i> -Ethyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (29) (95)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (11)	15	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-4-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (30) (20) and <i>N</i> -4-methylphenyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (31) (70)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (12)	5	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-2-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (33) (95)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (13)	1	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (35) (93)
<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (14)	6	<i>N</i> -4-Methylphenyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide (36) (87)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (15)	5	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (37) (6) and <i>N</i> -benzyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (45) (70)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (16)	2	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-2,5-dihydroxybenzamide (46) (95)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (17)	2	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (39) (98)
<i>N</i> -Benzyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (18)	7	<i>N</i> -Benzyl-4-acetoxy-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (40) and <i>N</i> -benzyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide (41)**
<i>N</i> -Methyl- <i>N</i> -phenyl-2-acetoxybenzamide (19)	6	<i>N</i> -Methyl- <i>N</i> -phenyl-2-hydroxybenzamide (42) (80)

*No deacetylation reaction was observed on any of the above substrates by carrying out reactions under similar conditions but without addition of the CCL.

**Obtained as an inseparable mixture of two in the ratio 1 : 1.

It has been observed that the selectivity of PPL for deacetylation of *ortho*-acetoxy function increases when the substituent at the amidic nitrogen is changed from ethyl to 4-methylphenyl group. Thus, deacetylation of *N*-4-methylphenyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (11) and *N*-4-methylphenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (12) in the presence of PPL in THF afforded the *ortho*-hydroxybenzamides 30 and 32 in 70 and 65% yields, together with 2,4-dihydroxybenzamide 31 and 2-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide 33 in 5 and 15% yields respectively (Table 1). PPL in THF also recognises one among the two identical *meta*-acetoxy functions of *N*-4-methylphenyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (13), but failed to recognise among the two *meta*- and a *para*-acetoxy functions of *N*-4-methylphenyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (14) affording *N*-4-methylphenyl-3-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (34) and *N*-4-methylphenyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide

(35) in 30 and 35% yields, and *N*-4-methylphenyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide (36) in 30% yield respectively. The deacetylation of *N*-4-methylphenyl benzamides 11, 13 and 14 catalysed by CRL afforded the completely deacetylated benzamides 31, 35 and 36 as the major or exclusive products, whereas *N*-4-methylphenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (12) afforded exclusively *N*-4-methylphenyl-2-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (33) in 95% yield (Table 2). Though the selectivity of PPL in THF and CRL in DIPE for deacetylation of different acetoxy functions of the *N*-benzylbenzamides 15 and 16 are different, it is identical in the case of the benzamide 17 (Tables 1 and 2).

During the deacetylation of *N*-benzyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (18), both PPL and CRL discriminate among the two *meta*- and one *para*-acetoxy functions of the triacetate and catalyse the deacetylation of two *meta*-acetoxy groups faster than the deacetylation of *para*-acetoxy function leading to the formation of an inseparable mixture of *N*-benzyl-4-acetoxy-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (40) and *N*-benzyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide (41). The mixture of 40 and 41 could not be separated by column chromatography or preparative thin layer chromatography. The ratio of the two compounds, 40 and 41 in the mixtures obtained by deacetylation of 18 catalysed by PPL and CRL was found to be 3 : 1 and 1 : 1 respectively, on the basis of respective intensities of the peaks for the benzylic protons (at δ 4.25 and 4.40) in the ^1H nmr spectra of the two mixtures. The nmr spectra of both the mixtures were identical except for the intensities of the peaks indicating that the chemical components of both the mixtures are the same. The monoacetoxybenzamide 40 and trihydroxybenzamide 41 in the mixtures were identified on the basis of their spectral analysis, the ^1H nmr spectra of both the mixtures exhibited only one singlet at δ 6.90 due to two equivalent aromatic protons of the benzoic acid moiety. This indicates that both the components of the mixture are symmetrically substituted, this leaves only two probable structures for the deacetylation products of 18, i.e. the corresponding trihydroxybenzamide and the monoacetoxydihydroxybenzamide bearing the acetoxy group at the C-4 position. If any of the components were an unsymmetrical acetate, the two aromatic protons should have resonated at two different chemical shift values as these are magnetically non-equivalent. Further, the two *ortho*-protons (with respect to the carbonyl group) of the benzoic acid moiety in the triacetoxymethylbenzamide 18 resonated at lower field (δ 7.54) with respect to the chemical shift values of the same protons in the two mixtures (δ 6.90). This is indicative of the fact that the two *meta*-acetoxy functions of 18 are deacetylated in both the products. The ^{13}C nmr spectra of the mixtures exhibited two peaks at δ 42.11

and 42.46 corresponding to the two benzylic carbons of the two compounds, the presence of benzylic carbons was also confirmed in the DEPT nmr spectra of the two mixtures. Again, the formation of 3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide was also confirmed by the observance of NaOAc + H₃BO₃ induced bathochromic shift of 16 nm in the uv-spectrum of the mixture of **40** and **41** obtained by the CRL-catalysed deacetylation of **18**. The mass spectra of both the mixtures exhibited peaks at *m/z* 301 (of very weak intensity) corresponding to the molecular ion peak of the mono-acetoxybenzamide **40** and the base peak at *m/z* 259 corresponding to the molecular ion peak of the trihydroxybenzamide **41** and the peak corresponding to the [M-42]⁺ fragment of the monoacetoxybenzamide **40**.

The deacetylation of sole acetoxy function of tertiary benzamide *N*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-2-acetoxybenzamide (**19**) is faster with CRL in DIPE than with PPL in THF; thus incubation of **19** with CRL and PPL for the same period of time afforded the hydroxy compound **42** in 80 and 49% yields, respectively. The deacetylation of *N*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**20**) and *N*-acetyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**21**) with PPL in THF is regioselective and gave *N*-methyl-*N*-phenyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (**43**) and *N*-acetyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (**44**) in 15 and 52% yields respectively. No deacetylation reaction was observed on any of the above substrates by carrying out the reactions under identical conditions and for the same length of time but without addition of the lipase (PPL or CRL).

19; R=OCOCH₃, R₁=H
20; R=R₁=OCOCH₃
42; R=OH, R₁=H
43; R=OH, R₁=OCOCH₃

21; R=R₁=COCH₃
44; R=H, R₁=COCH₃

All sixteen acetoxybenzamides **6-21**, and twenty two hydroxybenzamides and their partial acetylated derivatives, i.e. compounds **23**, **25-30** and **32-46** are new compounds and have been identified from their ¹H nmr, ¹³C nmr, ir, uv and EI mass spectral data. Although the benzamides, 2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (**22**)²¹, 3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (**24**)²² and *N*-4-methylphenyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (**31**)¹⁹ are known, their complete spectral data have not so far been published. We herein report their different spectral data (*cf.* Experimental). The presence of hydroxyl groups at *ortho*-, *meta*- or *para*-positions with respect to the nuclear amidic carbonyl group in the products of deacetylation reactions was established on the basis of their TLC behaviour and their reactions with Fe³⁺ when sprayed with 3% alcoholic

FeCl₃ solution and further supported by the observance of bathochromic shifts in their uv-absorption maxima in the presence of different uv-shift reagents (NaOAc, NaOMe, AlCl₃ or NaOAc + H₃BO₃)²³. The presence or absence of the corresponding peak due to chelated hydroxyl group in the ¹H nmr spectra also indicated whether the position *ortho* to the amidic carbonyl group is carrying the hydroxyl or the acetoxy group in different benzamides.

The random deacetylation of peracetylated primary, secondary and tertiary benzamides catalysed by PPL in THF is in conformity with our earlier proposed mechanism of action of porcine pancreatic lipase¹¹. These results further substantiate the formation of dynamic Schiff's base complex between the ε-amino group of the lysine residue in the active site of the enzyme and the ketonic carbonyl group directly attached to the benzenoid ring to impart high degree of regioselectivity during the deacetylation of peracetates of polyhydroxyaryl alkyl ketones and benzopyranones in organic solvents⁶⁻¹¹. In the present study, amidic carbonyl group can not form Schiff's base as effectively as the carbonyl group of aromatic ketones and benzopyranones and hence amides affected random orientation of different acetoxy groups of peracetylated polyhydroxy benzamides in the active site of the lipase resulting in their random deacetylation. In all deacetylation reactions, the amido group remained inert to enzymatic hydrolysis.

The enzymatic methodology developed and reported in this paper is the first demonstration of a useful and efficient synthetic method for the preparation of hydroxy and partially acetylated benzamides in as high yields as 98 and 95% respectively. Very few hydroxy/acetoxybenzamides, as evident from number of new compounds obtained during these enzymatic deacetylation studies, have so far been prepared, may be due to lack of efficient synthetic strategies. This methodology could find applications in the synthesis of selectively acetylated benzamides to be used in the multistep synthesis of nitrogen containing bioactive molecules and as well to produce libraries of hydroxy, acetoxybenzamides for structure-activity relationship studies. During the course of present biocatalytic deacetylation studies, thirty eight new compounds (**6-21**, **23**, **25-30** and **32-46**) have been prepared.

Experimental

Melting points were determined either in a bath or on a Mettler FP62 instrument and are uncorrected. The uv and ir spectra were recorded on a Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer and a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer respectively. The ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra were recorded either on a Bruker AC-250 or a Bruker AC-400 spectrometer at 250 and 400 MHz, and at 62.8 and 100 MHz respectively, using TMS

as internal standard; the chemical shift values are on δ scale and the coupling constants (J) are in Hz. The EI mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol JMSDX303 or on a Jeol AX 505W instrument at 70 eV. The enzymes, porcine pancreatic lipase (PPL, Type II) and *Candida rugosa* lipase (CRL, Type VII) (Sigma) were used after keeping *in vacuo* over P_2O_5 for 24 h. The organic solvents (THF and DIPE) used were distilled and dried over molecular sieves (4 Å), while *n*-butanol was dried and distilled over ignited potassium carbonate. Analytical TLCs were performed on silica gel coated on 5×20 cm glass plates and/or on precoated Merck silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ plates; the developing agents were alcoholic $FeCl_3$ solution (3%) or iodine vapour. All reactions were monitored on a Shimadzu LC-10AS HPLC instrument with SPD-10A uv-vis detector and Shimpack CLC-ODS (4.6×150 mm) reverse phase column. Solvent system used for HPLC was methanol-water (7 : 3) at the flow rate of 0.75 ml min^{-1} and monitored at λ_{254} nm. The peracetylated hydroxybenzoic acids **1b-5b** were prepared by stirring a solution of the hydroxybenzoic acids **1a-5a** in acetic anhydride in presence of catalytic amount of concentrated H_2SO_4 either at room temperature or at $40-50^\circ$ in high yields.

General method of preparation of peracetylated benzoic acid chlorides 1c-5c : Compounds **1c-5c** were prepared by refluxing a solution of the corresponding peracetylated hydroxybenzoic acids **1b-5b** (4 mmol) in thionyl chloride (6 mmol) for 3 h. Acid chlorides were obtained as light brown viscous oils after distilling off excess of thionyl chloride *in vacuo*. The crude acid chlorides thus obtained were directly used for the next step.

General method of preparation of primary amides 6, 7 and 21 : To the acid chlorides **2c-4c** (2 mmol), excess of 30% aq. ammonia solution was added dropwise over a period of 15–20 min maintaining the temperature below 5° , the temperature of the reaction mixture was then allowed to rise to 25° and it was stirred for 2 h. The mixture was neutralized with dil. HCl, extracted with ethyl acetate (2×75 ml) and the organic layer was washed with $NaHCO_3$ solution (75 ml), dried over Na_2SO_4 and concentrated under reduced pressure to give a mixture of hydroxy- and acetoxybenzamides as white solids. This mixture was dissolved in excess of acetic anhydride and stirred for 20–24 h in the presence of catalytic amount of *N,N*-dimethylaminopyridine to afford pure peracetylated primary amides **6** and **7** after column chromatography on silica gel in 65–70% yields. In the course of acetylation of the mixture of hydroxy- and acetoxybenzamides obtained from aminolysis of 2,5-diacetoxybenzoyl chloride (**3c**), *N*-acetyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (**21**) was obtained exclusively.

2,4-Diacetoxybenzamide (6) : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 79° ; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3520, 3310, 1770,

1680, 1640, 1590, 1230, 1130, 1020 and 800 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 310, 306, 303, 298 and 296 nm ; 1H nmr (400 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 2.29 and 2.43 (6H, 2s, 3H each, $2 \times OCOCH_3$), 6.80 (2H, m, C-3H and C-5H), 7.90 (1H, d, J 9.0 Hz, C-6H) and 10.80 and 11.85 (2H, 2 br s, 1H each, CONH₂); ^{13}C nmr (100 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 21.08 and 26.63 ($2 \times OCOCH_3$), 111.10 and 114.40 (C-3 and C-5), 116.80 (C-1), 132.86 (C-6), 155.62 (C-2), 158.77 (C-4), 165.40 and 169.51 ($2 \times OCOCH_3$) and 172.70 (CONH₂); m/z (% rel. int.) 237 ($[M]^+$, 10), 195 ($[M-CH_2CO]^+$, 19), 178 (24), 153 ($[M-2 \times CH_2CO]^+$, 53), 136 ($[M-2 \times CH_2CO-NH_3]^+$, 100), 121 (12), 108 ($[M-2 \times CH_2CO-NH_3-CO]^+$, 35) and 95 (5).

3,5-Diacetoxybenzamide (7) : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 153° ; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3430, 3240, 1785, 1710, 1640, 1230, 1165, 940 and 760 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 280 and 270 nm ; 1H nmr (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.28 (6H, s, $2 \times OCOCH_3$), 7.19 (1H, t, J 2.0 Hz, C-4H), 7.50 (1H, br s, CONH), 7.55 (2H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-2H and C-6H) and 8.05 (1H, br s, CONH); ^{13}C nmr (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.85 ($2 \times OCOCH_3$), 118.62 (C-2 and C-6), 119.00 (C-4), 136.43 (C-1), 150.80 (C-3 and C-5), 165.98 ($2 \times OCOCH_3$) and 169.06 (CONH₂); m/z (% rel. int.) 237 ($[M]^+$, 8), 195 ($[M-CH_2CO]^+$, 39), 153 ($[M-2 \times CH_2CO]^+$, 95), 137 (35), 125 (4), 109 (7), 91 (5), 81 (2), 69 (15) and 43 (100).

***N*-Acetyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (21)** : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. $132-34^\circ$; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3320, 1770, 1720, 1640, 1260, 1180, 1070 and 920 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 280, 273, 266 and 262 nm ; 1H nmr (250 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 2.31 and 2.36 (6H, 2s, 3H each, $2 \times OCOCH_3$), 2.55 (3H, s, $NCOCH_3$), 7.19 (1H, d, J 8.8 Hz, C-3H), 7.30 (1H, dd, J 2.7 and 8.8 Hz, C-4H), 7.61 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz, C-6H) and 8.90 (1H, br s, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 20.94 and 25.56 ($2 \times OCOCH_3$ and $N-COCH_3$), 123.52, 124.71 and 126.80 (C-3, C-4 and C-6), 126.97 (C-1), 145.56 (C-2), 148.34 (C-5), 162.66 ($NHCOCH_3$), 168.40 and 168.93 ($2 \times OCOCH_3$) and 172.64 (NHCO); m/z (% rel. int.) 279 ($[M]^+$, 2), 237 ($[M-CH_2CO]^+$, 35), 195 ($[M-2 \times CH_2CO]^+$, 53), 178 (12), 167 (4), 153 ($[M-3 \times CH_2CO]^+$, 90), 136 ($[M-3 \times CH_2CO-NH_3]^+$, 100), 108 ($[M-3 \times CH_2CO-NH_3-CO]^+$, 10), 80 (3), 60 (13) and 43 (34).

General method of preparation of secondary and tertiary amides 8-20 :

The acid chlorides **1c-5c** (2 mmol) were dissolved in dry benzene (80 ml) and equivalent amount of a mixture of the required amine (ethylamine, 4-methylaniline, benzylamine or *N*-methylaniline) and triethylamine (1 : 1) was added dropwise through a dropping funnel over a period of 15–20 min. The solution was refluxed for 8 h, benzene distilled off, the residue extracted with ethyl acetate (2×50

ml) and the organic layer was washed sequentially with dilute HCl (2 × 50 ml), saturated NaHCO₃ solution (2 × 50 ml) and finally with brine (2 × 50 ml). Removal of the solvent under reduced pressure afforded a mixture of hydroxy- and acetoxybenzamides as dirty white solids. *N*-Ethylbenzamides were prepared by refluxing a mixture of neat acid chlorides with ethylamine affording a mixture of *N*-ethylhydroxy- and acetoxybenzamides. The mixtures of hydroxy- and acetoxybenzamides of primary and secondary amines were dissolved in excess of acetic anhydride and stirred for 20–24 h in the presence of catalytic amount of *N,N*-dimethylaminopyridine to afford the pure peracetates 8-20 after column chromatographic purification over silica gel in 50–60% yields.

***N*-Acetyl-*N*-ethyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (8) :** Obtained as an orange oil; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3370, 1782, 1680, 1640, 1600, 1260, 1200, 1040 and 905 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 283, 261 and 254 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.14 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.25, 2.26 and 2.30 (9H, 3s, 3H each, 2 × OCOCH₃ and NCOCH₃), 3.73 (2H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 7.05 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz, C-3H), 7.11 (1H, dd, *J* 2.0 and 8.4 Hz, C-5H) and 7.50 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, C-6H); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 14.03 (CH₃), 20.62, 20.98 and 26.07 (2 × OCOCH₃ and NCOCH₃), 40.94 (CH₂), 116.87 (C-3), 119.30 (C-5), 126.46 (C-1), 129.48 (C-6), 148.31 (C-2), 153.09 (C-4), 168.23, 168.30 and 169.79 (2 × OCOCH₃ and NCOCH₃) and 172.95 (CONH); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 307 ([M]⁺, 1), 265 (15), 248 (22), 223 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 55), 181 ([M-2 × CH₂CO]⁺, 100), 163 (6), 137 (50), 136 (22), 108 (7), 107 (4), 88 (5), 70 (3), 43 (15) and 40 (4).

***N*-Acetyl-*N*-ethyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (9) :** Obtained as an orange oil; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3330, 1795, 1680, 1640, 1565, 1240, 1150, 960 and 790 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 279, 262 and 237 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 1.08 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.21, 2.22 and 2.28 (9H, 3s, 3H each, 2 × OCOCH₃ and NCOCH₃), 3.64 (2H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, CH₂CH₃) and 7.27–7.38 (3H, m, C-3H, C-4H and C-6H); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 13.59 (CH₃), 20.32, 20.62 and 25.16 (2 × OCOCH₃ and NCOCH₃), 40.06 (CH₂), 121.72 (C-3), 124.18 and 124.89 (C-4 and C-6), 130.43 (C-1), 143.80 (C-2), 147.63 (C-5), 168.30, 168.63 and 168.95 (2 × OCOCH₃ and NCOCH₃) and 172.39 (CONH); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 307 ([M]⁺, 1), 265 (12), 248 (13), 223 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 40), 181 ([M-2 × CH₂CO]⁺, 100), 163 (15), 138 (25), 136 (25), 135 (12), 108 (5), 107 (4), 84 (100), 80 (3), 79 (3), 66 (92), 57 (15) and 43 (21).

***N*-Ethyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (10) :** Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 125°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3315, 1780, 1650, 1581, 1200, 1050, 940 and 720 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 278 and 245 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 1.13

(3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.29 (6H, s, 2 × OCOCH₃), 3.31 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 7.15 (1H, t, *J* 2.1 Hz, C-4H), 7.57 (2H, d, *J* 2.1 Hz, C-2H and C-6H) and 8.57 (1H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz, NH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 14.44 (CH₃), 20.56 (2 × OCOCH₃), 34.14 (CH₂), 118.10 (C-2 and C-6), 118.53 (C-4), 136.57 (C-1), 150.66 (C-3 and C-5), 163.88 (CONH) and 168.82 (2 × OCOCH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 265 ([M]⁺, 12), 223 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 92), 181 ([M-2 × CH₂CO]⁺, 100), 180 (28), 153 (11), 137 (35), 136 (9), 109 (11), 108 (4), 81 (3), 69 (6) and 43 (26).

***N*-4-Methylphenyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (11) :** Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 118–19°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3440, 1785, 1640, 1560, 1210, 1130, 1020, 940, 820 and 700 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 291, 287, 265 and 252 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 2.19 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.26 and 2.29 (6H, 2s, 3H each, CH₃ and OCOCH₃), 7.04–7.35 (4H, m, C-3H, C-5H, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.60 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H) and 7.73 (1H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, C-6H); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 20.36, 20.51 and 20.68 (2 × OCOCH₃ and CH₃), 117.05 (C-3), 119.26 and 119.73 (C-3', C-5' and C-5), 127.27 (C-4'), 128.94 (C-2' and C-6'), 129.76 (C-6), 132.58 (C-1'), 136.42 (C-1), 148.60 (C-2), 152.01 (C-4), 164.32 (CONH), and 168.67 and 168.92 (2 × OCOCH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 327 ([M]⁺, 4), 285 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 25), 243 ([M-2 × CH₂CO]⁺, 3), 240 (7), 221 (5), 179 (12), 137 (32), 107 (100), 77 (5), 60 (5), 44 (16), 43 (7) and 40 (17).

***N*-4-Methylphenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (12) :** Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 134°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3320, 1785, 1660, 1600, 1520, 1240, 1040, 952 and 720 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 298, 264 and 258 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 2.19 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.26 and 2.29 (6H, 2s, 3H each, OCOCH₃ and CH₃), 7.13 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.30–7.32 (2H, m, C-3H and C-4H), 7.45 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, C-6H) and 7.56 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 20.36, 20.50, 20.64 (2 × OCOCH₃ and CH₃), 119.84 (C-3' and C-5'), 122.16 (C-6), 124.15 and 124.71 (C-3 and C-4), 128.95 (C-2' and C-6'), 130.46 (C-4'), 132.72 (C-1'), 136.27 (C-1), 145.25 (C-2), 147.44 (C-5), 162.85 (CONH), 168.74 and 169.04 (2 × OCOCH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 327 ([M]⁺, 8), 285 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 45), 243 ([M-2 × CH₂CO]⁺, 50), 221 (3), 179 (13), 149 (4), 137 (18), 136 (4), 107 (100), 106 (15), 77 (2), 60 (5) and 43 (8).

***N*-4-Methylphenyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (13) :** Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 152–53°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3405, 1795, 1640, 1600, 1550, 1215, 1190, 1140, 1010, 910 and 680 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 300, 296, 286 and 263 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 2.28 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.31 (6H, s, 2 × OCOCH₃), 7.15 (2H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.26 (1H, t, *J* 2.0 Hz, C-4H) and 7.63–7.67

(4H, m, C-2H, C-2'H, C-6H and C-6'H); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.36 and 20.64 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$ and CH_3), 118.53 (C-2 and C-6), 119.07 (C-4), 120.40 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.91 (C-2' and C-6'), 132.87 (C-4'), 136.15 and 136.81 (C-1 and C-1'), 150.66 (C-3 and C-5), 163.15 (CONH) and 168.82 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 327 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 100), 285 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 79), 243 ($[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 64), 221 (32), 179 (71), 137 (93), 109 (14), 107 (11), 79 (3), 60 (9) and 43 (21).

N-4-Methylphenyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (14) : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 147°; ν_{max} (nujol) 3450, 1780, 1660, 1600, 1200, 1060 and 710 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 312, 308 and 298 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.28 (3H, s, CH_3), 2.33 and 2.34 (9H, 2s of 6H and 3H, $3 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 7.17 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.64 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H), 7.84 (2H, s, C-2H and C-6H) and 10.05 (1H, s, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 19.73 (CH_3), 20.17, 20.37 and 20.55 ($3 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 118.91 (C-2 and C-6), 120.41 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.95 (C-2' and C-6'), 132.88 and 132.94 (C-4 and C-4'), 136.12 and 137.12 (C-1 and C-1'), 143.01 (C-3 and C-5), 162.78 (CONH), and 166.86 and 167.91 ($3 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 385 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 32), 343 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 24), 301 ($[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 18), 259 ($[\text{M}-3 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 100), 237 (12), 195 (16), 153 (22), 107 (40), 106 (7), 79 (2), 60 (2) and 43 (17).

N-Benzyl-2,4-diacetoxybenzamide (15) : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 91°; ν_{max} (nujol) 3402, 1775, 1710, 1640, 1570, 1330, 1280, 1185, 960, 910, 805 and 720 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 324 (sh), 273 and 261 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.11 and 2.27 (6H, 2s, 3H each, $2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.42 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 7.07 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-3H), 7.14 (1H, dd, J 2.0 and 8.3 Hz, C-5H), 7.16–7.34 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 7.65 (1H, d, J 8.3 Hz, C-6H) and 8.85 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.47 and 20.67 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 42.32 (CH_2), 117.04 (C-3), 119.23 (C-5), 126.65 (C-4'), 126.80 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.13 (C-2' and C-6'), 128.25 (C-1), 129.58 (C-6), 139.23 (C-1'), 148.49 (C-2), 151.84 (C-4), 164.57 (CONH), and 168.47 and 168.67 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 327 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 10), 285 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 83), 243 ($[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 76), 221 (31), 179 (19), 177 (8), 137 (56), 136 (10), 108 (9), 107 (16), 106 (44), 91 (100), 79 (4), 65 (5) and 43 (16).

N-Benzyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (16) : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 112°; ν_{max} (nujol) 3400, 1785, 1640, 1540, 1375, 1210, 1170, 1005, 940, 820 and 705 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 305, 275 and 260 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.11 and 2.27 (6H, 2s, 3H each, $2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.40 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 7.24–7.37 (8H, m, C-3H, C-4H, C-6H and C_6H_5) and 8.86 (1H, t, J

6.0 Hz, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.45 and 20.62 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 42.36 (CH_2), 121.95 (C-3), 124.21 and 124.48 (C-4 and C-6), 126.67 (C-4'), 127.15 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.13 (C-2' and C-6'), 130.02 (C-1'), 139.11 (C-1), 145.14 (C-2), 147.43 (C-5), 164.15 (CONH), and 168.73 and 169.01 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 327 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 2), 285 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 30), 243 ($[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 63), 226 (3), 225 (1), 179 (2), 137 (6), 136 (8), 108 (5), 107 (3), 106 (10), 91 (100), 79 (3), 65 (4) and 43 (8).

N-Benzyl-3,5-diacetoxybenzamide (17) : Obtained as a semi-solid; ν_{max} (nujol) 3380, 1785, 1770, 1660, 1600, 1560, 1340, 1220, 1160, 1040, 860 and 707 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 279, 275 and 265 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.28 (6H, s, $2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.50 (2H, d, J 5.9 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 7.22 (1H, t, J 2.0 Hz, C-4H), 7.24–7.34 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 7.64 (2H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-2H and C-6H) and 9.16 (1H, t, J 5.9 Hz, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.60 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 42.80 (CH_2), 118.31 (C-2 and C-6), 118.81 (C-4), 126.76 (C-4'), 127.27 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.18 (C-2' and C-6'), 136.29 (C-1'), 139.21 (C-1), 150.77 (C-3 and C-5), 164.27 (CONH) and 168.83 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 327 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 100), 285 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 80), 243 ($[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 63), 179 (7), 137 (25), 109 (8), 106 (81), 91 (74), 69 (4) and 43 (21).

N-Benzyl-3,4,5-triacetoxybenzamide (18) : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 108°; ν_{max} (nujol) 3310, 1785, 1640, 1610, 1560, 1205, 1090, 1050, 920 and 730 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 324 (sh), 274 and 265 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 2.26 and 2.28 (9H, 2s of 6H and 3H, $3 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 4.56 (2H, d, J 5.7 Hz, $\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$), 6.54 (1H, t, J 5.7 Hz, NH), 7.25–7.34 (5H, m, C_6H_5) and 7.54 (2H, s, C-2H and C-6H); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 20.10 and 20.52 ($3 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 44.26 (CH_2), 119.67 (C-2 and C-6), 127.66, 127.91 and 128.76 (C-2', C-3', C-4', C-5' and C-6'), 132.55 (C-1), 136.50 (C-1'), 137.68 (C-4), 143.49 (C-3 and C-5), 164.96 (CONH) and 166.53 and 167.68 ($3 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 385 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 20), 343 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 28), 301 ($[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 56), 259 ($[\text{M}-3 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 100), 195 (2), 153 (4), 125 (5), 106 (17), 91 (45), 60 (3) and 43 (24).

N-Methyl-N-phenyl-2-acetoxybenzamide (19) : Obtained as a semi-solid; ν_{max} (nujol) 1780, 1640, 1600, 1240, 1160, 1100 and 740 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 284, 277, 265 and 261 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.30 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 3.45 (3H, s, NCH_3) and 7.11–7.26 (9H, m, C-3H, C-4H, C-5H, C-6H and C_6H_5); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 21.02 (OCOCH_3), 39.36 (NCH_3), 122.65 (C-3), 124.98 (C-1), 126.33 and 126.54 (C-4, C-5 and C-6), 128.92 (C-2', C-3', C-5' and C-6'), 130.02 (C-4'), 143.69 (C-1'), 147.68 (C-2), and 167.27 and 168.79 (CON and OCOCH_3); m/z (% rel. int.) 269 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 19), 227 ($[\text{M}-$

$\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 55), 211 (3), 163 (15), 121 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5]^+$, 95), 107 (100), 106 (15), 93 (1), 77 (10), 65 (7), 44 (6) and 43 (5).

N-Methyl-N-phenyl-2,5-diacetoxybenzamide (20) : Obtained as a red oil; ν_{max} (nujol) 3100, 1775, 1640, 1590, 1410, 1356, 1200, 1160, 1000, 900 and 760 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 276, 263 and 256 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.18 and 2.28 (6H, 2s, 3H each, $2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 3.43 (3H, s, NCH_3) and 6.89–7.28 (8H, m, C-3H, C-4H, C-6H and C_6H_5); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 20.78 and 20.88 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$), 37.57 (NCH_3), 122.99 and 123.39 (C-3 and C-4), 126.20 and 126.86 (C-6 and C-4'), 128.99 (C-2', C-3', C-5' and C-6'), 129.60 (C-1), 143.15 (C-1'), 144.67 (C-2), 147.09 (C-5), 166.23 (CONH) and 168.53 ($2 \times \text{OCOCH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 327 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 7), 285 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 38), 243 ($[\text{M}-2 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 37), 221 (3) 179 (28), 137 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-\text{CH}_3\text{NC}_6\text{H}_5]^+$, 32), 107 (100), 106 (14), 77 (6) and 43 (12).

General method of enzymatic deacetylation of benzamides 6-21 :

The peracetylated benzamide (1.0 mmol) was dissolved in dry tetrahydrofuran or diisopropyl ether (20–30 ml) containing n-butanol (4 mol eqv.) and porcine pancreatic lipase or *Candida rugosa* lipase (200 mg each) was added. The suspension was stirred at 42–45° and progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC and/or HPLC. After completion, the reaction was quenched by filtering off the lipase, solvent removed under reduced pressure and the crude products were purified by preparative TLC or column chromatography and/or by crystallisation to afford pure deacetylated benzamides 22-46.

2,4-Dihydroxybenzamide (22) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 225° (lit.²¹ 228–29°); ν_{max} (KBr) 3475, 3375, 1650, 1560, 1440, 1275, 1000 and 780 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 296, 268 and 257; $+\text{AlCl}_3$: 320, 314 and 280; $+\text{NaOAc}$: 295, 260 and 154; $+\text{NaOMe}$: 314, 308 and 299 nm; ^1H nmr (400 MHz, acetone- d_6) δ 6.34 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-3H), 6.37 (1H, dd, J 2.0 and 8.0 Hz, C-5H), 6.97 (1H, br s, OH), 7.65 (1H, br s, CONH), 7.69 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, C-6H), 9.17 (1H, br s, CONH) and 12.88 (1H, br s, chelated OH); ^{13}C nmr (100 MHz, acetone- d_6) δ 103.82 (C-3), 107.08 (C-1), 107.79 (C-5), 129.95 (C-6), 163.52 (C-2), 165.17 (C-4) and 173.82 (CONH $_2$); m/z (% rel. int.) 153 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 32), 136 ($[\text{M}-\text{NH}_3]^+$, 38), 108 ($[\text{M}-\text{NH}_3-\text{CO}]^+$, 35), 91 (40), 78 (92), 63 (100) and 48 (92).

2-Acetoxy-4-hydroxybenzamide (23) : Obtained as a white semi-solid; ν_{max} (KBr) 3475, 3375, 1740, 1646, 1640, 1615, 1377, 1240, 1023 and 760 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 302, 279, 262 and 256; $+\text{NaOAc}$: 310, 301 and 295; $+\text{NaOMe}$: 374, 353 and 323 nm; ^1H nmr (400 MHz, MeOH- d_4) δ 2.46 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 6.35 (1H, d, J 2.0

Hz, C-3H), 6.43 (1H, dd, J 2.0 and 8.5 Hz, C-5H) and 7.84 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, C-6H); ^{13}C nmr (100 MHz, MeOH- d_4) δ 25.82 (OCOCH_3), 103.81 (C-3), 109.27 (C-1), 109.51 (C-5), 133.24 (C-6), 162.50 (C-2), 165.45 (C-4), 168.20 (OCOCH_3) and 174.57 (CONH $_2$); m/z (% rel. int.) 195 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 13), 178 ($[\text{M}-\text{NH}_3]^+$, 8), 177 (12), 153 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 61), 136 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-\text{NH}_3]^+$, 100), 108 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-\text{NH}_3-\text{CO}]^+$, 62), 95 (13), 80 (22), 69 (26) and 43 (82).

3,5-Dihydroxybenzamide (24)²² : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 240°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3540, 3320, 3120, 1680, 1615, 1520, 1440, 1320, 1175, 1030 and 875 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 301, 268 and 260; $+\text{NaOAc}$: 301, 265 and 260; $+\text{NaOMe}$: 355, 322, 272 and 268 nm; ^1H nmr (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 6.34 (1H, br s, C-4H), 6.68 (2H, br s, C-2H and C-6H), 7.15 and 7.72 (2H, 2s, 1H each, $2 \times \text{OH}$) and 9.41 (2H, s, NH $_2$); ^{13}C nmr (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 105.25 and 105.86 (C-2, C-4 and C-6), 136.70 (C-1) and 158.29 (C-3 and C-5); m/z (% rel. int.) 153 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 62), 136 ($[\text{M}-\text{NH}_3]^+$, 69), 108 ($[\text{M}-\text{NH}_3-\text{CO}]^+$, 10), 97 (12), 69 (21), 60 (18), 55 (32), 43 (100) and 41 (30).

N-Ethyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (25) : Obtained as a yellow crystalline solid, m.p. 151–52°, ν_{max} (KBr) 3400, 3220, 1660, 1600, 1560, 1275, 1175, 990 and 810 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 295, 264, 257 and 246; $+\text{AlCl}_3$: 317, 269, 259 and 231; $+\text{NaOAc}$: 260, 252 and 249; $+\text{NaOMe}$: 310, 275, 231 and 224 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 1.14 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 3.31 (2H, m, CH_2CH_3), 6.28 (1H, d, J 2.3 Hz, C-3H), 6.31 (1H, dd, J 2.3 and 8.7 Hz, C-5H), 7.70 (1H, d, J 8.7 Hz, C-6H) and 8.53 (1H, t, J 5.3 Hz, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 14.59 (CH_3), 33.61 (CH_2), 102.75 (C-3), 106.61 (C-1), 106.87 (C-5), 128.73 (C-6), 162.14 and 162.69 (C-2 and C-4) and 169.29 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 181 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 80), 137 (100), 136 (35), 109 (5), 108 (12), 81 (7), 69 (5), 53 (3) and 46 (8).

N-Ethyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (26) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 101–02°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3402, 3065, 2985, 1758, 1718, 1615, 1603, 1423, 1296, 1013 and 822 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (MeOH) 325; $+\text{AlCl}_3$: 343, 338 and 327; $+\text{NaOAc}$: 325; $+\text{NaOMe}$: 359 and 354 nm; ^1H nmr (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 1.13 (3H, t, J 6.0 Hz, CH_2CH_3), 2.25 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 3.34 (2H, m, CH_2CH_3), 6.92 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, C-3H), 7.19 (1H, dd, J 2.0 and 8.0 Hz, C-4H), 7.62 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-6H), 8.80 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, NH) and 9.98 (1H, br s, chelated OH); ^{13}C nmr (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 14.48 (CH_3), 20.74 (OCOCH_3), 34.02 (CH_2), 115.33 (C-1), 118.12 (C-3), 120.45 (C-4), 127.40 (C-6), 141.94 (C-5), 157.76 (C-2), and 167.90 and 169.60 ($2 \times \text{CO}$); m/z (% rel. int.) 223 ($[\text{M}]^+$, 20), 181 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}]^+$, 100), 163 (23), 136 ($[\text{M}-\text{CH}_2\text{CO}-\text{NH}_2\text{C}_2\text{H}_5]^+$, 92), 108

([M-CH₂CO-C₂H₅NH₂-CO]⁺, 13), 79 (10), 69 (7), 53 (21), 46 (65) and 43 (45).

N-Ethyl-2,5-dihydroxybenzamide (27) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 145–46°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3375, 3100, 1650, 1610, 1500, 1340, 1140, 940, 805 and 620 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 346, 317, 247 and 238; +AlCl₃ : 364, 359 and 241; +NaOAc : 323, 241 and 235; +NaOMe : 355 and 243 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 1.14 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 3.28 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 6.74 (1H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz, C-3H), 6.88 (1H, dd, *J* 2.8 and 8.8 Hz, C-4H), 7.25 (1H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz, C-6H), 8.70 (1H, t, *J* 5.3 Hz, NH) and 9.02 (1H, br s, OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 14.47 (CH₃), 33.77 (CH₂), 113.11 (C-3), 115.51 (C-1), 117.71 (C-4), 121.16 (C-6), 149.09 (C-2), 152.52 (C-5) and 168.41 (CO); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 181 ([M]⁺, 100), 163 (18), 149 (10), 136 ([M-CH₃CH₂NH₂]⁺, 90), 108 ([M-CH₃CH₂NH₂-CO]⁺, 16), 80 (7), 60 (5) and 46 (28).

N-Ethyl-3-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (28) : Obtained as a yellow semi-solid; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 3272, 2926, 2854, 1770, 1645, 1615, 1455, 1372, 1215, 1145, 1023, 905 and 766 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 291, 268 and 260; +NaOAc : 291, 259 and 229; +NaOMe : 327, 323, 286 and 253 nm; ¹H nmr (200 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 1.14 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 2.30 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 3.27 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 6.65 (1H, t, *J* 2.0 Hz, C-6H), 7.05 (1H, t, *J* 2.0 Hz, C-4H), 7.16 (1H, t, *J* 2.0 Hz, C-2H), 8.40 (1H, t, *J* 5.3 Hz, NH) and 9.98 (1H, br s, OH); ¹³C nmr (50 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 15.56 (CH₃), 21.70 (OCOCH₃), 34.93 (CH₂), 111.99 (C-4), 112.44 (C-2), 112.73 (C-6), 137.65 (C-1), 151.99 (C-3), 159.05 (C-5), 165.82 (CONH) and 169.94 (OCOCH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 223 ([M]⁺, 23), 181 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 100), 137 (80), 136 ([M-CH₂CO-C₂H₅NH]⁺, 6), 109 (20), 81 (10) and 57 (5).

N-Ethyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (29) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 117–19°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3400, 3200, 3021, 1660, 1610, 1377, 1160, 1000, 850 and 675 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 297, 244 and 226; +NaOAc : 298, 244 and 228; +NaOMe : 325, 247 and 237 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 1.14 (3H, t, *J* 7.2 Hz, CH₂CH₃), 3.26 (2H, m, CH₂CH₃), 6.41 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz, C-4H), 6.73 (2H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz, C-2H and C-6H), 8.28 (1H, t, *J* 5.3 Hz, NH) and 9.48 (2H, s, 2 × OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 14.83 (CH₃), 34.13 (CH₂), 105.10 (C-4), 105.55 (C-2 and C-6), 137.08 (C-1), 158.33 (C-3 and C-5) and 166.55 (CO); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 181 ([M]⁺, 73), 180 (22), 137 (100), 136 ([M-C₂H₅NH₂]⁺, 4), 109 (30), 108 (3), 81 (6), 69 (9) and 44 (8).

N-4-Methylphenyl-4-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (30) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 195–96°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3350, 3050, 2975, 1750, 1600, 1525, 1310, 1210, 1125 and 975 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 312, 307, 304 and 300;

+AlCl₃ : 342, 323 and 285; +NaOAc : 340, 323, 301 and 294; +NaOMe : 350, 321, 317 and 312 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2.28 (6H, s, OCOCH₃ and CH₃), 6.75 (1H, dd, *J* 2.3 and 8.0 Hz, C-5H), 6.78 (1H, d, *J* 2.3 Hz, C-3H), 7.18 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.59 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H), 8.02 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz, C-6H), 10.67 (1H, s, chelated OH) and 12.45 (1H, br s, NH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 20.36 and 20.76 (OCOCH₃ and CH₃), 110.25 (C-3), 112.62 (C-5), 115.00 (C-4'), 120.93 (C-3' and C-5'), 129.00 (C-2' and C-6'), 129.91 (C-6), 133.21 (C-1'), 135.39 (C-1), 154.08 (C-2), 159.67 (C-4), 165.89 (OCOCH₃) and 168.56 (CONH); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 285 ([M]⁺, 24), 243 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 4), 179 (2), 138 (1), 137 (33), 108 (10), 107 (100), 106 (17), 81 (3), 69 (1) and 43 (2).

N-4-Methylphenyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (31) : Obtained as a brown solid, m.p. 178° (lit.¹⁹ 178–79°); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3564, 3372, 2924, 1654, 1600, 1548, 1313, 1257 and 849 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 309, 301 and 295; +AlCl₃ : 344, 323 and 299; +NaOAc : 301 and 285; +NaOMe : 345, 322 and 299 nm; ¹H nmr (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2.27 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.30 (1H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz, C-3H), 6.34 (1H, dd, *J* 8.6 and 2.8 Hz, C-5H), 7.17 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.57 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H), 7.87 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, C-6H), 10.07 (2H, br s, 2 × OH) and 10.15 (1H, br s, NH); ¹³C nmr (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 20.58 (CH₃), 102.91 (C-3), 107.51 (C-5), 107.92 (C-6), 117.11 (C-4'), 121.32 (C-3' and C-5'), 129.17 (C-2' and C-6'), 130.51 (C-1), 133.26 (C-1'), 161.89 (C-2), 162.61 (C-4) and 169.38 (CO); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 243 ([M]⁺, 41), 179 (3), 137 (90), 107 (100), 106 (90), 91 (6), 81 (28), 69 (14) and 53 (18).

N-4-Methylphenyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (32) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 184°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3501, 3411, 3039, 1658, 1608, 1490, 1285, 1220, 995 and 887 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 323, 318 and 301; +AlCl₃ : 355, 347 and 283; +NaOAc : 320, 299 and 287; +NaOMe : 353, 297 and 288 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2.27 and 2.29 (6H, 2s, 3H each, CH₃ and OCOCH₃), 7.02 (1H, d, *J* 8.6 Hz, C-3H), 7.18 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.22 (1H, dd, *J* 2.8 and 8.6 Hz, C-5'H), 7.59 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H), 7.74 (1H, d, *J* 2.8 Hz, C-6H) and 10.70 (1H, s, chelated OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 20.36 and 20.57 (CH₃ and OCOCH₃), 117.58 and 117.80 (C-3 and C-4'), 120.81 (C-3' and C-5'), 121.52 (C-6), 127.09 (C-4), 129.03 (C-2' and C-6'), 133.26 (C-1'), 135.35 (C-1), 142.23 (C-5), 155.94 (C-2), 165.28 (OCOCH₃) and 169.38 (CONH); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 285 ([M]⁺, 28), 243 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 35), 179 (2), 137 (15), 107 (100), 106 (19), 91 (2), 79 (2) and 43 (3).

N-4-Methylphenyl-2-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide

(33) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 151°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3327, 3176, 1769, 1659, 1450, 1284, 1182, 1012 and 813 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 282, 272 and 258; +NaOAc : 284, 279 and 257; +NaOMe : 375, 323, 287 and 263 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.13 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.26 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.92 (1H, dd, J 3.0 and 8.6 Hz, C-4H), 7.02 (2H, m, C-3H and C-6H), 7.12 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.57 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H), 9.77 (1H, br s, NH) and 10.14 (1H, s, OH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.36 and 20.49 (OCOCH₃ and CH₃), 114.95 (C-4), 117.46 (C-6), 119.70 (C-3' and C-5'), 123.93 (C-3), 128.90 (C-2' and C-6'), 130.20 (C-4'), 132.45 (C-1'), 136.47 (C-1), 139.93 (C-2), 154.66 (C-5), 163.75 (OCOCH₃) and 169.08 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 285 ([M]⁺, 24), 243 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 41), 179 (4), 137 (18), 107 (100), 77 (2), 65 (1) and 43 (4).

N-4-Methylphenyl-3-acetoxy-5-hydroxybenzamide (34) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 209–10°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3367, 3035, 1714, 1615, 1595, 1515, 1211, 1133, 1019, 980 and 820 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 282, 270 and 266; +NaOAc : 283, 263 and 253; +NaOMe : 355, 280, 263 and 253 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.27 (6H, s, OCOCH₃ and CH₃), 6.73 (1H, t, J 2.0 Hz, C-4H), 7.16 (3H, m, C-2H, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.23 (1H, t, J 2.0 Hz, C-6H), 7.63 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H), and 10.21 and 10.29 (2H, 2s, 1H each, NH and OH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.38 and 20.74 (CH₃ and OCOCH₃), 111.44, 111.97 and 112.16 (C-2, C-4 and C-6), 120.29 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.87 (C-2' and C-6'), 132.58 (C-1'), 136.37 and 136.92 (C-4' and C-1), 151.09 (C-3), 158.03 (C-5), 164.22 (OCOCH₃) and 168.92 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 285 ([M]⁺, 60), 243 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 61), 179 (37), 137 (100), 109 (16), 83 (5), 60 (8), 44 (21) and 43 (17).

N-4-Methylphenyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (35) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 106–10°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3600, 3460, 3275, 1675, 1600, 1550, 1360, 1175, 1020 and 820 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 305, 289 and 283; +NaOAc : 285 and 282; +NaOMe : 325 and 285 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.26 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.36 (1H, t, J 2.0 Hz, C-4H), 6.66 (2H, d, J 2.0 Hz, C-2H and C-6H), 7.10 (2H, d, J 8.3 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.63 (2H, d, J 8.3 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H) and 9.82 (1H, br s, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.36 (CH₃), 105.16 and 105.79 (C-2, C-4 and C-6), 120.05 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.75 (C-2' and C-6'), 132.03 (C-1'), 136.81 (C-1 and C-4'), 159.48 (C-3 and C-5) and 165.95 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 243 ([M]⁺, 62), 138 (6), 137 (100), 109 (17), 107 (7), 106 (6), 81 (3), 69 (3) and 44 (7).

N-4-Methylphenyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide (36) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 177–78°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3315, 3158, 1646, 1592, 1404, 1325, 1193 and 1038 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max}

(MeOH) 311, 303 and 298; +NaOAc; 313, 310 and 298; +NaOAc + H₃BO₃ : 323, 318 and 308; +NaOMe ; 410, 390, 330, 284 and 279 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.26 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.94 (2H, s, C-2H and C-6H), 7.12 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, C-3'H and C-5'H), 7.60 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, C-2'H and C-6'H), 8.90 (3H, br s, 3 × OH) and 9.79 (1H, br s, NH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.35 (CH₃), 107.05 (C-2 and C-6), 120.06 (C-3' and C-5'), 125.05 (C-4), 128.74 (C-2' and C-6'), 131.87 (C-4'), 136.53 and 136.95 (C-1 and C-1'), 145.35 (C-3 and C-5) and 165.28 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 259 ([M]⁺, 45), 153 (32), 125 (11), 107 (100), 106 (25), 79 (6), 77 (4) and 44 (4).

N-Benzyl-4-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (37) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 155–56°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3344, 3033, 2942, 1757, 1597, 1439, 1307, 1235, 1146, 1015 and 800 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 330, 325; +AlCl₃ : 339, 333 and 325; +NaOMe : 332 and 326 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.26 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.53 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH₂C₆H₅), 6.70 (1H, dd, J 2.3 and 8.5 Hz, C-5H), 6.72 (1H, d, J 2.3 Hz, C-3H), 7.25–7.35 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 7.94 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, C-6H), 9.33 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, NH) and 12.62 (1H, s, chelated OH); ^{13}C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.79 (OCOCH₃), 42.31 (CH₂), 110.43 (C-3), 112.50 and 113.00 (C-1 and C-5), 126.87 (C-4'), 127.19 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.30 (C-2' and C-6'), 128.90 (C-6), 138.82 (C-1'), 154.31 (C-4), 161.01 (C-2), 168.31 and 168.59 (2 × CO); m/z (% rel. int.) 285 ([M]⁺, 78), 243 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 61), 226 (7), 177 (3), 137 (40), 106 (32), 91 (100), 79 (4), 65 (6) and 43 (8).

N-Benzyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (38) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 170–71°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3354, 3068, 1759, 1641, 1597, 1548, 1375, 1214, 1018 and 930 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 326; +AlCl₃ : 339 and 334; +NaOMe : 374, 352 and 348 nm; ^1H nmr (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 2.26 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.51 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH₂C₆H₅), 6.69 (2H, m, C-4H and C-6H), 7.23–7.34 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 7.94 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, C-3H), 9.32 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, NH) and 9.78 (1H, br s, chelated OH); ^{13}C nmr (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 20.97 (OCOCH₃), 42.45 (CH₂), 110.60 (C-3), 112.68 (C-4), 113.16 (C-6), 127.03 (C-4'), 127.33 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.47 (C-2' and C-6'), 129.06 (C-1'), 138.97 (C-1), 154.44 (C-5), 161.22 (C-2), and 168.44 and 168.77 (2 × CO); m/z (% rel. int.) 285 ([M]⁺, 22), 243 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 18), 181 (5), 137 (30), 136 (25), 91 (100), 77 (8), 65 (4), 51 (8) and 43 (26).

N-Benzyl-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (39) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 92–93°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3375, 3201, 1640, 1600, 1377, 1175, 1000 and 920 cm^{-1} ; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 298 and 268; +NaOAc : 298, 269 and 266; +NaOMe : 322, 275, 269 and 254 nm; ^1H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ

4.46 (2H, d, J 5.9 Hz, CH₂), 6.45 (1H, t, J 1.1 Hz, C-4H), 6.80 (2H, br s, C-2H and C-6H), 7.18–7.32 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 8.86 (1H, t, J 5.9 Hz, NH) and 9.54 (2H, br s, 2 × OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 42.52 (CH₂), 105.19 (C-4), 105.52 (C-2 and C-6), 126.62 (C-4'), 127.08 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.17 (C-2' and C-6'), 136.60 (C-1'), 139.70 (C-1), 158.28 (C-3 and C-5) and 166.59 (CO); m/z (% rel. int.) 243 ([M]⁺, 93), 137 (51), 106 (100), 91 (14), 79 (6), 69 (6) and 44 (6).

N-Benzyl-4-acetoxy-3,5-dihydroxybenzamide (40) + *N-Benzyl-3,4,5-trihydroxybenzamide* (41)²⁴ : Obtained as a white solid and found to be a mixture of compounds 40 and 41 in a ratio of 1 : 1, m.p. 104–07°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3392, 2925, 1760, 1635, 1519, 1314, 1180, 1079, 1025, 871 and 737 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 298, 266 and 246; +NaOAc : 296, 293, 267 and 252; +NaOAc + H₃BO₃ : 314, 310, 306 and 296; +NaOMe : 415, 323, 293, 287 and 279 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 1.97 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 4.25 (2H, d, J 5.6 Hz, CH₂), 4.40 (2H, d, J 5.8 Hz, CH₂), 6.90 (s, C-2H and C-6H), 7.21–7.35 (10H, m, 2 × C₆H₅), 8.33 (1H, t, J 5.6 Hz, NH) and 8.63 (1H, t, J 5.8 Hz, NH) and 9.16 (br s, OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 22.51 (OCOCH₃), 42.11 and 42.46 (2 × CH₂), 106.78 (C-2 and C-6), 124.43, 126.53, 126.69, 127.07, 127.22, 128.14, 128.23, 136.29, 139.51, 140.29 and 145.42 (aromatic carbons), 166.41 (OCOCH₃) and 169.24 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 301 (1), 259 (100), 258 (10), 153 (60), 125 (20), 106 (86), 91 (18), 79 (14), 51 (5), 43 (3) and 39 (4).

N-Methyl-N-phenyl-2-hydroxybenzamide (42) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 118°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3275, 1650, 1610, 1490, 1240, 1150 and 750 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 284 and 281; +AlCl₃ : 341 and 324; +NaOMe : 314, 305 and 300 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 3.48 (3H, s, NCH₃), 6.38 (1H, dt d, J 1.3, 0.8 and 1.2 Hz, C-5H), 6.63 (1H, dd, J 1.6 and 8.0 Hz, C-3H), 6.93 (1H, dd, J 1.3 and 8.2 Hz, C-4H), 7.10–7.18 (3H, m, C-3'H, C-4'H and C-5'H) and 7.22–7.35 (3H, m, C-6H, C-2'H and C-6'H); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 39.24 (NCH₃), 117.64 and 117.79 (C-1 and C-3), 126.62 (C-3', C-5 and C-5'), 127.11 (C-6), 129.64 (C-2' and C-6'), 130.33 (C-4'), 132.66 (C-4), 145.17 (C-1'), 160.65 (C-2) and 171.49 (CON); m/z (% rel. int.) 227 ([M]⁺, 25), 121 ([M-CH₃NC₆H₅]⁺, 33), 107 (100), 106 (20), 93 (11), 65 (11), 44 (3) and 39 (5).

N-Methyl-N-phenyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (43) : Obtained as an orange solid, m.p. 77–80°; ν_{\max} (CHCl₃) 3360, 2956, 1769, 1690, 1595, 1501, 1200, 1160 and 886 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 297, 290 and 261; +AlCl₃ : 367, 353, 324 and 297; +NaOAc : 295 and 261; +NaOMe : 352, 344, 337 and 323 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 2.07 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 3.47 (3H, s, NCH₃), 6.35 (1H, dd,

J 1.1 and 2.0 Hz, C-6H), 6.89 (2H, m, C-3H and C-4H), 7.09–7.13 (2H, m, C-3'H and C-5'H) and 7.26–7.35 (3H, m, C-2'H, C-4'H and C-6'H); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, CDCl₃) δ 20.63 (OCOCH₃), 39.21 (NCH₃), 115.95 (C-1), 118.34 (C-3), 122.81 (C-4), 126.11 (C-6), 126.42 (C-3' and C-5'), 127.31 (C-4'), 129.73 (C-2' and C-6'), 141.06 (C-1'), 144.48 (C-5), 158.20 (C-2), and 169.12 and 170.37 (OCOCH₃ and CON); m/z (% rel. int.) 285 ([M]⁺, 28), 243 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 38), 179 (5), 149 (3), 137 ([M-CH₂CO-NCH₃C₆H₅]⁺, 22), 107 (100), 106 (18), 77 (5), 44 (6) and 43 (3).

N-Acetyl-5-acetoxy-2-hydroxybenzamide (44) : Obtained as a brown solid, m.p. 122–25°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3405, 3283, 2923, 1785, 1730, 1680, 1600, 1377, 1196, 1026, 915 and 832 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 312 and 271; +AlCl₃ : 358, 276 and 262; +NaOMe : 422, 353, 276 and 256 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 2.25 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.38 (3H, s, NCOCH₃), 7.05 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, C-3H), 7.24 (1H, dd, J 3.0 and 8.0 Hz, C-4H), 7.63 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz, C-6H) and 10.82 (1H, s, chelated OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 20.58 (OCOCH₃), 25.56 (NCOCH₃), 117.85 (C-3), 118.32 (C-1), 123.03 (C-4), 127.85 (C-6), 142.69 (C-5), 154.34 (C-2), 164.01 (NCOCH₃), 169.28 (OCOCH₃) and 171.57 (CON); m/z (% rel. int.) 237 ([M]⁺, 12), 195 ([M-CH₂CO]⁺, 40), 153 ([M-2 × CH₂CO]⁺, 70), 136 ([M-2 × CH₂CO-NH₃]⁺, 100), 108 (10), 97 (6), 81 (5), 71 (5), 57 (7) and 43 (25).

N-Benzyl-2,4-dihydroxybenzamide (45) : Obtained as a white crystalline solid, m.p. 94°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3590, 3410, 2956, 1660, 1600, 1520, 1410, 1285, 1000 and 830 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 307, 303 and 296; +AlCl₃ : 330, 323, 316 and 306; +NaOAc : 302, 294 and 270; +NaOMe : 323, 316 and 304 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 4.47 (2H, d, J 6.0 Hz, CH₂), 6.27 (1H, d, J 2.1 Hz, C-3H), 6.32 (1H, dd, J 2.1 and 8.5 Hz, C-5H), 7.23–7.26 (5H, m, C₆H₅), 7.74 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, C-6H), 9.08 (1H, t, J 6.0 Hz, NH) and 9.73 and 10.11 (2H, 2br s, 1H each, 2 × OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 42.28 (CH₂), 102.91 (C-3), 106.69 and 107.25 (C-5 and C-6), 126.98 (C-4'), 127.36 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.47 (C-2' and C-6'), 129.17 (C-1'), 139.40 (C-1), 162.48 and 162.74 (C-2 and C-4) and 169.49 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 243 ([M]⁺, 45), 137 (41), 106 (32), 91 (100), 81 (10), 65 (10), 51 (11) and 43 (8).

N-Benzyl-2,5-dihydroxybenzamide (46) : Obtained as a white solid, m.p. 166–67°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3364, 2946, 1654, 1615, 1533, 1363, 1318, 1240, 1136, 984, 876 and 778 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 337, 334, 223 and 261; +AlCl₃ : 371, 365 and 356; +NaOAc : 328 and 323; +NaOMe : 355 and 323 nm; ¹H nmr (250 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 4.50 (2H, d, J 5.9 Hz, CH₂), 6.76 (1H, d, J 8.5 Hz, C-3H), 6.89 (1H, dd,

J 2.8 and 8.5 Hz, C-4H), 7.21–7.37 (6H, m, C₆H₅ and C-6H), 9.02 (1H, br s, OH), 9.21 (1H, t, J 5.9 Hz, NH) and 11.29 (1H, s, chelated OH); ¹³C nmr (62.8 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 42.31 (CH₂), 113.39 (C-3), 115.67 (C-4), 117.75 (C-6), 121.27 (C-4'), 126.78 (C-1'), 127.17 (C-3' and C-5'), 128.26 (C-2' and C-6'), 139.07 (C-1), 149.24 (C-2), 152.21 (C-5) and 168.31 (CONH); m/z (% rel. int.) 243 ([M]⁺, 62), 137 (7), 136 (12), 106 (9), 92 (9), 91 (100), 81 (2), 79 (3) and 65 (5).

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